

Figure 11a: The round temple base, method 1, MY 5.94.

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To make a round temple base from a square:

Make a square $abcd$. Measure the diagonal bc . Halve that length to get $1/2bc$. Subtract $1/8^{\text{th}}$ from $1/2bc$. Use the resulting length $(1/2bc - 1/8bc)$ as the radius, ef , of a circle around the centre of the square, e .